

1 **Soil priorities for the Czech Republic**

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10 **Introduction**

11 The Czech Republic has an area of 78,871 km², out of which 53.3% is agricultural land (including 37.5%
12 of arable land and 13.0% of grassland), 33.9% forest area, 2.1% water bodies, and 10.7% built-up and
13 other areas (Ministry of Agriculture, 2018). Dominant soil unit is Cambisol forming about one half of
14 the total area; other soil classes like Gleysols, Stagnosols, Chernozems, Fluvisols, Luvisols or Podzols
15 cover much smaller areas, no more than 8% each (Kozák et al., 2010). Elevation ranges from 115 to
16 1603 m a.s.l. Climate is mostly warm-summer humid continental. Current soil priorities can be divided
17 into two groups: 1) soil survey, monitoring, data collection and soil assessment, and 2) soil degradation
18 mitigation, soil conservation and protection and sustainable soil management.

19 **Soil data collection**

20 There is a unique and long tradition of soil surveys in the area of the Czech Republic, which resulted in
21 a large amount of legacy soil data from various resources (Table 1; Borůvka et al., 2018). Systematic
22 Soil Survey of agricultural land with almost 400 thousands of sampled and analysed soil pits was done
23 in 1960s, agrochemical soil testing is done regularly on all agricultural land since 1962, agricultural land

24 valuation surveys started in 1970s, basal soil monitoring is also done on agricultural land (Borůvka et
25 al., 2018). Similarly, the forest soils are surveyed in frame of the National Forest Inventory, forest soil
26 monitoring is focused on areas impacted by acid deposition (Borůvka et al., 2022); moreover, the
27 country participates on several international soil surveys like LUCAS, ICP-Forests and Biosoil etc.
28 (Borůvka et al., 2018). However, there is no unified database, the soil data are scattered in several
29 databases managed by different institutions. Moreover, the methodology of soil surveys and analyses
30 differs, and many data are significantly aged. As a consequence, it is difficult to collect and combine
31 existing data into one soil database system. Available soil data, if they should be compiled into one
32 database, need standardization and harmonization. Update of old legacy data and temporal changes
33 quantification are necessary (Zádorová et al., 2021). New sources of soil and related data should be
34 exploited, like remote and proximal soil sensing or digital terrain models. Recently, new detailed maps
35 of agricultural soils based on the legacy soil data and auxiliary environmental information and
36 exploiting the digital soil mapping methods were created (Žížala et al., 2022). Development and
37 adoption of a unified methodology would be very useful for soil surveys in the near future, from
38 sampling design, through laboratory analytical methods, to processing of results. These approaches
39 could enable creation of a harmonized soil database and a complex soil information system (Zádorová
40 et al., 2021) and, if combined with digital soil mapping tools, development of soil property maps
41 tailored to the user needs like maps of soil organic carbon stocks and sequestration potential, or maps
42 of hydropedological characteristics. It would be useful for all potential users, from farmers,
43 environmentalists, to policy makers. It would be also helpful for international cooperation, knowledge
44 sharing and exchange, and collaborative projects.

45 **Soil conservation and protection and soil management**

46 The biggest issues in soil sustainable management and soil degradation in the Czech Republic are soil
47 water erosion and reduced water retention in soils. Soil water erosion endangers 53.8% of agricultural
48 land, out of which 15.0% strongly, and 2,8% very strongly to critically (Ministry of Agriculture, 2018). A

49 lot of research is focused on the factors, processes and consequences of soil water erosion and on
50 activities to mitigate it, including governmental regulations aiming in erosion reduction. A large part of
51 agricultural land is impacted also by soil compaction and soil structure destruction (e.g. Pavlů et al.,
52 2022). Large farms of several thousands of hectares farming on rented land are more susceptible to
53 soil degradation than smaller and family farms farming on their own land; however, almost 80% of
54 agricultural land in the Czech Republic is farmed by tenants (Sklenička et al., 2020).

55 Land take and soil sealing is another big threat. Political changes in 1989 followed by high real estate
56 development led to a large land take and soil sealing. Mean loss of arable land was more than 20ha
57 per day in the last 20 years, and unfortunately, a big part of it is the most valuable land with most
58 fertile soils (Janků et al., 2016; Ministry of Agriculture, 2018).

59 Soil pollution with potentially toxic elements and organic pollutants is a problem in some regions and
60 locations like hotspots only. New attention is paid to pharmaceuticals, nanoplastics, and other
61 emerging pollutants which can present an issue in soil protection and a risk of groundwater pollution
62 and food contamination, particularly due to application of treated wastewater for irrigation or various
63 biosolids as soil amendments (Kodešová et al., 2019).

64 In forest soils, a big problem is strong acidity of many stands due to high acid deposition in the second
65 half of the 20th century and accumulation of sulphur in forest soils. Deposition of nitrogen compounds
66 is still rather high and leads to imbalance in tree nutrition due to the deficiency of available phosphorus
67 and magnesium in many forest soils (e.g. Novotný et al., 2020).

68 Two soil issues are closely related to climate change. First, increased drought in both agricultural and
69 forest soils in recent years, which is a consequence of climate change. It causes big impacts on
70 agricultural production as well as on forest tree growth and on the whole forest ecosystem. It is
71 supported by low water retention ability of soils and by low infiltration, partially due to soil compaction
72 (e.g. Trnka et al., 2018). Soil water retention as well as water infiltration are frequently aggravated by
73 soil erosion (Nikodem et al., 2021). In terms of potential water scarcity, extensive drainage systems,

74 moreover in a bad technical state due to insufficient maintenance, are also a problem. Another issue
75 that should on the other hand mitigate climate change and that gains more and more attention
76 recently is carbon sequestration and the ways how to increase it. The Czech soil science community
77 follows the global trends to apply various computer models to describe soil processes and to provide
78 reliable prediction of soil properties in time and space for various climatic scenarios.

79 **Concluding remarks**

80 Sustainable soil management, both in agriculture and forestry, is crucial for keeping efficient and
81 sustainable production on soils, while keeping soils healthy, able to provide all the other, particularly
82 ecosystem services, including soil carbon sequestration, biodiversity protection, and water retention
83 and purification. Many issues are dealt with in the new EU Soil Strategy (EC, 2021) and in national
84 legislation (for example limited size of land parcels in areas endangered by water erosion, minimizing
85 bare soil periods, obligation of organic fertilization on agricultural soils, etc.). Harmonization of soil
86 surveys and databases, continuation and possibly extension of long-term soil monitoring and
87 agrochemical soil testing, and exploitation of advances in remote and proximal sensing for cost-
88 efficient soil data collection are big tasks for the broader soil community. New approach to soil
89 valuation taking into account the environmental soil functions and ecosystem services is another
90 challenge. International cooperation and knowledge exchange and participation on continental-scale
91 soil surveys and international research projects is very important. Nevertheless, keeping soils healthy
92 is not possible without an increase of public awareness and education on all levels leading to general
93 understanding of soil importance for humans.

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Table 1. Description of the principal soil surveys and databases in the Czech Republic (adapted and amended from Borůvka et al., 2018).

Dataset	Extent	Land-use	Number of locations	Density (area per sample)	Sampling scheme	Time collected	Repeated/cycle length	Organic horizons ^a	Topsoil depth (horizon/cm)	Subsoil depth (horizon/cm)	Data ownership/management ^b
Systematic soil survey	national	agricultural	36,942 ^b	30-180 ha ^c	purposive	1960-1970	no	-	A	all horizons	MA/RISWC
Agrochemical soil testing	national	agricultural	~70,000/yr	2-10 ha	even	1962+	6 yrs	-	0-30 ^d	-	MA/UKZUZ
Soil monitoring	national	agricultural	187 (+27 polluted areas)	-	purposive	1992+	6 yrs	-	0-30	30-60 ^e	MA/UKZUZ
Forest soil survey	national	forest	~200/yr	-	even	1996+	irregular	F+H	0-10	10-40	MA/UKZUZ
Permanent testing areas	national	forest	140	-	purposive	1980s+	irregular	F, H	0-10	10-40	MA/FMI
National forest inventory	national	forest	~1,600	4 x 4 km	even	2011-2015 ^f	~10 yrs	H	A	all horizons	MA/FMI
ICP Forest	European	forest	120+	8 x 8 km ^g	even	1986+	10 yrs ^h	L, F, H	0-10	10-20 ⁱ	FGMRI
BioSoil	European	forest	146	16 x 16 km	purposive	2005-2008	No ^j	F+H	0-10	10-20, 20-40, 40-80	FGMRI
LUCAS	European	all	430	14 x 14 km	regular grid	2009+	~6 yrs	-	0-20	-	EU/JRC
Forest soil pollution survey	national	forest	120	-	stratified random	2011-2012	no	F+H	0-2	2-10, 10-20, 20-40	CZU, FGMRI, RISWC, MU
INTERREG	regional	all	~250	8 x 8 km	regular grid	2006-2008	no	-	A	all horizons	UKZUZ

^a L, F, H – samples collected separately by horizons, F+H – mixed samples collected.

^b MA – Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, RISWC – Research Institute for Soil and Water Conservation, UKZUZ – Central Institute for Supervising and Testing in Agriculture, FMI – Forest Management Institute, FGMRI – Forestry and Game Management Research Institute, EC – European Commission, JRC – Joint Research Center Ispra, Italy, CZU – Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, MU – Masaryk University Brno.

^c The total number of sampling pits was 386,615 (corresponding to 3-18 ha per pit), but only on 36,942 profiles the full analysis was done.

^d These depths are used for arable land and orchards. On grasslands, the sampled depth is 0-15 cm, on hop-fields 10-40 cm, and two depths (0-30, 30-60 cm) are sampled on vineyards.

^e The whole profiles (all horizons) were sampled and analyzed once at the beginning of monitoring.

^f The first National forest inventory was done in 2001-2004, but it used a different methodology.

^g 8 x 8 km is the densest grid, but the soil pits were not dug on all nodes. Original grid at the first survey in 1986 and at some repetitions was 16 x 16 km.

^h A part of locations (subset Intensive Monitoring ICP Forests) is sampled every 5 years.

ⁱ Deep sampling to 1 m with 10cm intervals on a point basis was done once at the beginning of monitoring.

^j BioSoil is considered as a repetition of the ICP Forests.